

Impact of climate change on Saint Martin's Island of Bangladesh

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Abstract

The study aims to assess the impact of climate change on Saint Martin's Island, where soft coral is available. Both primary and secondary data were used to examine the current changes and to predict the future changes in the ecosystem. It was found that the mangrove forests are near to extinct due to anthropogenic and climatic perturbations. The climatic factors include sedimentations, inundation stress and increased salinity at landward zones. Pandanus trees face high level of mortality due to increased salinity. The nut development of coconut tree is affected by water stress which resulted in a small number of nuts, empty nuts or elongated nuts. The major threats to the corals are high levels of sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges and beach erosion. The study advocated for adopting a mitigation strategy to overcome these stresses.

Keywords: Climate change, corals, mangrove, coconut, salinity, mitigation

Introduction

Bangladesh faces unpredictable climate change impacts for a long that is subject to multiple stressors originating from a rapidly changing environment (Rahman 2020, Rahman 2021a, Rahman 2022c) and social dynamics (Mitchell et al.2015, Rahman *et al.* 2009, Rahman 2021b, Rahman 2022a, b). Global climate change poses a high risk to the biodiversity of the coral of Saint Martin's. The major threats to the coral are high levels of sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges and beach erosion. Global warming is a matter of major concern for the coral of this island as elsewhere. Saint Martin's is a tiny island in the Bay of Bengal approximately 9 km south of Cox's Bazar-Teknaf peninsula. It is in the southernmost part of Bangladesh and is locally known as Narikel Jinjira (Coconut Island). Saint Martin's Island is a stock of extraterrestrial, marine and land resources (Rani *et al.* 2020). Depending on the tidal level the surface area is about 8 kilometres and the beach length is about 14 kilometres. This is the most attractive tourist spot in Bangladesh (Rahman 2021b).

The biodiversity of Saint Martin's Island is characterized by mangrove forests, seaweeds, corals, turtles, crabs, fish, seabirds, coconut trees and Pandanus vegetation. The island is a unique example of the co-occurrence of different ecosystems. Mangroves are home to corals, crabs, seaweeds and sea birds, and provide excellent nurseries for marine fishes. It also protects the inhabitants from storm surges, cyclones and tidal waves, and prevents the island from erosion. Screw pine (Pandanus) is one of the iconic tree species of this island. It grows on exposed mainland and along beaches and has thick 'prop roots' to anchor itself in the loose sand. The island is a congenial habitat of a diverse coral community represented by approximately 66 Scleractinian coral species, of which 19 are fossil corals, 36 are living corals and 11 are soft corals (Tomascik 1997). About 14% area of this island

is visited by 03 species of marine nesting turtles including Olive Ridley. All of them are considered globally endangered by IUCN.

This is also a suitable habitat for different species of multi- colour ornamental fishes. During the year 1997, 240 fish species were recorded from the catch landed on this island and 86 of them are coral-associated (Tomascik 1997). The abundant coral-associated fishes are Damsels, parrots, surgeons, Groupers, Snappers, Emperors and Butterfly fish (Haider 2008). 186 species of mollusc and oyster, 7 species of crab, 9 species of echinoderms, 4 species of sea urchin, 1 species of sea cucumber, some brittle stars, 5 species of marine mammals, some colourful nudibranch and bryozoans, 14 species of algae, 29 reptilian species and 120 species of birds (out of them 53 species are migratory) were recorded at the Saint Martin's Island. The biodiversity of this island is degrading day by day (Rahman 2021b). The study aimed to assess the impact of climate climatic stressors on the ecosystem of this Island.

Methodology

Both primary and secondary data were used for this study. The secondary data were collected from different academic sources and also national newspapers. The historical data was collected from the Forest Department. A focus group discussion was done incorporating the respondents from the diverse stakeholders. Total ten key informants were interviewed to understand the future projections and mitigation strategy. Content analysis was done to analyze the data.

Responses of biodiversity to climatic stressors

Coconut trees: Reproductive development of coconut trees is highly sensitive to high temperature and water stress. The fruit set is adversely affected, mainly due to a reduction in pollen viability. The nut development is affected mainly resulting in a small number of nuts, empty nuts or elongated nuts.

Mangrove forests: Sea level rise will cause a major threat to mangrove ecosystems through sediment erosion, inundation stress and increased salinity at landward zones. These problems will be exacerbated for the mangrove stands of this island due to the 'coastal squeeze' (landward migration is restricted by smaller size and human settlements). High rainfall and silts being washed down can also affect mangrove growth weakening its resilience.

Screw pine (Pandanus): Increasing salinity will cause high mortality of Pandanus trees. The removal of Pandanus trees will enhance beach and dune erosion.

Seaweed: Ozone layer depletion will allow a greater number of ultraviolet rays that can be harmful to seaweeds. UV rays decrease the photosynthesis and productivity of seaweeds and directly affect bio-molecules.

Sea algae: The respondents opined that 40% algae population may die due to climate change by the end of this century.

Coral: Global climate change poses a high risk to the biodiversity of the corals of Saint Martin's. The major threats to the corals are high levels of sedimentation, cyclones, storm surges and beach erosion. Global warming is a matter of major concern for the corals of this island as elsewhere. The most noticeable damage caused by high sea temperatures is coral bleaching. Coral bleaching turns into colourless ugly coral. Corals have already suffered major mortalities as a result of high-temperature events. It is also dependent on a species of algae that lives

symbiotically in its body and produces additional food by photosynthesis. When the sea temperature rises above 28°C, the coral expels the algae and consequently, it starves.

Turtle: Sea-level rise causes erosion of turtle nesting beaches. Higher sand temperature leads to changes in sex ratios or prevents eggs from hatching. Corals are essential feeding habitats for turtles. Coral bleaching destroys the feeding sources of turtles. Huge rainfall can raise groundwater tables, thereby flooding the nests of turtles.

Mollusc: Sea acidification will decline the abundance of a mollusc.

Crabs and shrimps: Due to sea level rise, the breeding place of crabs and shrimps will be destroyed.

Sea fish: Fishes will lose their habitats with coral bleaching and mangrove destruction.

Seabirds: High Sea temperature will affect seabird foraging success, growth patterns and reproductive potentiality. Coral bleaching increases surface temperature, which decreases breeding and populations of seabirds.

How to mitigate?

* To strengthen monitoring of biological resources and the impact of climate change for appropriate biodiversity management

* To develop alternative livelihoods for the people who are dependent on coral resources

- * To establish an appropriate conservation strategy
- * To emphasise the conservation programme of the coral ecosystem and protection of migratory birds
- * To keep the turtle's habitat undisturbed
- * To involve NGOs in the conservation programme
- * To establish an information system of biodiversity of this island
- * To strengthen research work on the impact of climate change
- * To emphasise ex-situ conservation of endangered species
- * To measure the adverse effects of natural calamities, global warming and sea level rise
- * To create public awareness by using different media
- * To raise funds for a conservation programme
- * To implement an ecosystem approach and community-based conservation programme by involving local people
- * To maintain and restore mangroves for reducing erosion
- * To establish mechanisms to promote carbon uptake

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